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Matr3, a component of the Xist RNP.

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We used genomic and proteomic methods to understand the full complement of molecular machines Xist interacted with in the Xist RNP that executes transcriptional regulation in somatic cells on the autosomes. Measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing and microarray in cells expressing an Xist transgene, in Xist+ human embryonic stem (hES) cell clones, and in cells with genetically engineered deletion of Xist (Xist knockout cells) demonstrated Xist regulated expressing of Matr3 and indicated that the Xist ncRNA interacted with matrin 3. Protein-protein interaction studies demonstrated Matr3 was an Xist-interacting protein. In humans with breast cancer, a matrin 3-containing Xist RNP complex appeared active in the luminal A subtype. Matr3 is an essential component of the Xist RNP that conducts gene silencing and activation in somatic cells and a Matr3-containing Xist RNP complex functions in subtype selection in luminal A subtype breast cancer.